

A New Era of Provenance Research? How the Yale Peabody Museum is looking at provenance today

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The term provenance has long been associated with art museums, but rarely do you find it used in the halls of natural history museums. However, the landscape is changing, and all museums are now under increased pressure to share as much information as possible about their stewarded collections. The terms ethical collecting and informed consent are becoming normalized within our field and more museums are beginning to surface their histories and examine past collecting and documentation practices. Additionally, museums are now, more than ever before, acknowledging the effects of those practices on source communities and the surrounding natural world.

With a Yale University-wide push to make provenance digitally accessible for Yale collections, initial phases of our work have focused on identifying ways to standardize our definitions of provenance across diverse collections, both within the Peabody, as well as across campus in art museums, libraries, and other physical collections. Making this information accessible requires a two-fold approach: addressing the lack of provenance documentation associated with legacy collections and setting in place procedures to vet new collections according to contemporary provenance standards. Through the lens of the Yale Peabody Museum, an institution that has historically amassed such diverse collections, we identify the methods, challenges, and successes experienced during the inception of this provenance initiative.

